

HETEROCYCLIC COMPOUNDS. PART XXIX. THE SYNTHESIS OF SUBSTITUTED 1-METHYL- AND 3-METHYL-1:2:3:4-TETRAHYDROACRIDONES

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1-Methyl-, 2-methyl- and 3-methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridones have been prepared from aniline and ethyl 6-methyl-, 5-methyl- and 4-methylcyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylates by the method of Conrad and Limpach. The tetrahydroacridones have been converted into their 5-chl roacridines for identification. The substituted derivatives of 1-methyl- and 3-methyltetrahydroacridones containing the substituents in the unreduced benzene ring have been prepared by condensing *o*- and *p*-toluidines, *o*- and *p*-anisidines, and *o*- and *p*-phenetidines with the corresponding cyclic β -ketonic esters and have been converted into their corresponding 5-chloroacridines.

Though 1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridones (I: $R_1=R_2=H$, hereafter called tetrahydroacridones) with substituents in the benzene ring are fairly well known, the number of those with the substituents in the reduced benzene ring is very small. Thus, Perkin and Sedgwick (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 2437) prepared 2-methyltetrahydro-5-acridone from *o*-aminobenzoic acid and 3-methylcyclohexanone, while Dasgupta and Basu (*this Journal*, 1937, 14, 468) prepared 2-methyl-7-chloro- and 2-methyl-7-methoxy-tetrahydro-5-acridones from ethyl 5-methylcyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylate and *p*-chloroaniline and *p*-anisidine by the method of Conrad and Limpach (*Ber.*, 1887, 20, 944). Buksh and Desai (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1939, 10A, 262) prepared 1-methyl- and 3-methyl-tetrahydroacridones by the application of Borche and Tiedke's method (*Ber.*, 1908, 41, 220; 1909, 42, 624).

In continuation of our previous work (*loc. cit.*) we have taken up the systematic investigation of the synthesis of some simple tetrahydroacridones with substituents in the reduced ring by the method of Conrad and Limpach.

Ethyl 6-methylcyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylate was condensed with aniline, *o*- and *p*-toluidines, *o*- and *p*-anisidines, *o*- and *p*-phenetidines at the room temperature by the method of Coffey, Thompson and Wilson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 856). The resulting ethyl 1-arylamino- $\Delta^{1:2}$ -6-methylcyclohexene-2-carboxylates (II) were cyclised by heating at 240°-250° to their respective 1-methyltetrahydro-5-acridones (I: $R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$).

[R = phenyl, *o*-tolyl, *p*-tolyl, *o*-methoxyphenyl etc.]

By heating with a mixture of phosphorus pentachloride and phosphorus oxychloride the tetrahydro-5-acridones were converted into their corresponding tetrahydro-5-chloro-

acridines, some of which were further characterised as anilino, *p*-toluidino and piperidino derivatives (III : R = phenyl or *p*-tolyl or piperidyl).

(III)

As some of the tetrahydroacridones have high m.p., these 5-chloroacridines or their arylamino derivatives, which have low melting points, are useful for their identification.

Ethyl 4-methylcyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylate has been condensed with arylamines, mentioned above, and the resulting arylamino-4-methylcyclohexene-2-carboxylates have been cyclised to 3-methyltetrahydro-5-acridone derivatives (I : R₁ = H ; R₂ = Me). These have been converted into the corresponding 3-methyltetrahydro-5-chloroacridines and 3-methyltetrahydro-5-arylaminoacridines. The work on the condensation of these arylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylates with amines at high temperatures and the conversion of the resulting anilides to the corresponding phenanthridones will be published in a later communication. The work described in this paper was completed twelve years ago, but owing to unavoidable circumstances the publication was delayed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 1-Anilino-Δ^{1:2}-6-methylcyclohexene-2-carboxylate (II : R = Ph).—A mixture of aniline (9.3 g.), ethyl 6-methylcyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylate (18.4 g.) and HCl (conc., 0.5 c.c.) was kept for 48 hours in a vacuum desiccator. The solid mass was washed with a small amount of petrol (b.p. 45°-50°) and the residue crystallised from rectified spirit in short needles, m.p. 95-96°, yield 8%. It is insoluble in dilute alkali solution, but dissolves in dilute HCl on warming and does not respond to alcoholic FeCl₃ colour reaction. (Found : C, 74.0; H, 8.3. C₁₈H₂₁O₂N requires C, 74.1; H, 8.1 per cent).

1-Methyltetrahydro 5-acridone.—The above solid (13.0 g.) was heated in an oil-bath at 240°-250° for 20 to 25 minutes, and cooled. The resulting solid crystallised from benzene in small, lustrous plates, m.p. 344-45°, yield 70%. It is soluble in hot dilute mineral acids, hot dilute alkali, but insoluble in sodium carbonate solution. It was identical in m.p. and mixed m.p. with a specimen prepared by Baksh and Desai (*loc. cit.*) from anthranilic acid and *O*-methylcyclohexanone. (Found : C, 78.7; H, 7.1. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₅ON : C, 78.9; H, 7.0 per cent).

TABLE I

M = methylcyclohexene-2-carboxylate. T = 1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-acridone. T ₁ = 1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-ch oroacridine.				
Compounds.	Formula.	Crystalline form.	M.P.	
			Analysis.	
			Found. Calc.	
1. 1- <i>p</i> -Tolimidino-Δ ¹ :3,6-M.	C ₁₇ H ₂₅ O ₂ N (80%)	Needles from alcohol.	119°	C: 74.7% H: 8.4
2. 1:1-Dimethyl-T.	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ ON (85%)	Colorless prisms.	268°	C: 79.2 H: 7.6
3. 1:7-Dimethyl-T.	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ NCI	Prisms from alcohol.	87°	Cl: 14.6
4. 1- <i>o</i> -Tolimidino-Δ ¹ :3,6-M.	C ₁₇ H ₂₅ O ₂ N (60%)	Needles from hexane.	134°	C: 74.8 H: 8.3
5. 1:9-Dimethyl-T.	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ ON (52%)	Needles from alcohol.	296°	C: 79.5 H: 7.4
6. 1:9-Dimethyl-T.	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ NCI	Small needles from petrol.	72°	Cl: 14.6
7. 1- <i>p</i> -Anisidino-Δ ¹ :3,6-M.	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ O ₂ N (50%)	Needles from alcohol.	92°	C: 70.4 H: 8.1
8. 1-Methyl-7-methoxy-T.	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	Do	257°	C: 73.9 H: 7.2
9. 1-Methyl-7-methoxy-T ₁ .	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ONCI	Prisms from alcohol.	81°	Cl: 13.8
10. 1- <i>o</i> -Anisidino-Δ ¹ :3,6-M.	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ O ₂ N (30%)	Needles from benzene.	89-90°	C: 70.4 H: 8.2
11. 1-Methyl-9-methoxy-T.	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₂ N (40%)	Needles from alcohol.	274°	C: 73.8 H: 6.9
12. 1-Methyl-9-methoxy-T ₁ .	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ONCI	White needles from alcohol.	98-99°	Cl: 13.7
13. 1- <i>p</i> -Phenetidino-Δ ¹ :3,6-M.	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ O ₂ N (65%)	Plates from alcohol	109-110°	C: 71.1* H: 8.2*
14. 1-Methyl-7-ethoxy-T.	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	Do	> 300°	C: 74.7 H: 7.4
15. 1-Methyl-7-ethoxy-T ₁ .	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ ONCI	Yellow needles from pet. ether.	92°	Cl: 13.0
16. 1- <i>o</i> -Phenetidino-Δ ¹ :3,6-M.	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ O ₂ N (50%)	Prisms from hexane.	114°	C: 71.2 H: 8.4
17. 1-Methyl-9-ethoxy-T.	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N	Colorless needles from alcohol.	251°	C: 74.6 H: 7.5
18. 1-Methyl-9-ethoxy-T ₁ .	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ONCI	Small prisms from alcohol.	100°	Cl: 13.1

* Figures in parenthesis denote % yield.

TABLE II
3-Methyltetrahydro-5-acridone and its derivatives.

Compounds,	Formula.	Crystalline form.	M.P.	Analysis,	
				Found.	Calc.
1. 1-Anilino- $\Delta^1:2,4$ -M.	$C_{16}H_{14}O_2N$ (80%)	Lustrous prisms from alcohol.	$106-107^\circ$	C: 74.2% H: 8.0	74.1% 8.1
2. 3-Methyl-T.	$C_{16}H_{15}ON$ (95%)	Plates from alcohol.	$> 350^\circ$	C: 78.7 H: 7.0	78.8 7.0
3. 3-Methyl-T.	$C_{16}H_{14}NCl$ (80%)	Yellowish plates from hexane.	64°	Cl: 15.4	15.3
4. 5-Anilino der. of (3).	$C_{16}H_{14}N_2$ (80%)	Feble yellow plates from benzene.	106°	N: 9.6	9.7
5. 5- β -Toluidino der. of (3).	$C_{17}H_{15}N_2$ (70%)	Yellow plates from benzene.	146°	N: 9.1	9.3
6. 5-Piperidino der. of (3).	$C_{19}H_{24}N_2$ (30%)	Orange needles from benzene.	151°	N: 9.7	10.0
7. 1- β -Toluidino- $\Delta^1:2,4$ -M.	$C_{17}H_{16}O_2N$ (75%)	Leaflets from benzene.	126°	C: 74.7 H: 8.6	74.7 8.4
8. 3:7-Dimethyl-T.	$C_{16}H_{17}ON$ (85%)	Plates from alcohol.	$> 310^\circ$	C: 79.1 H: 7.5	79.3 7.5
9. 3:7-Dimethyl-T.	$C_{16}H_{16}NCl$ (85%)	Prisms from alcohol.	88°	Cl: 14.7	14.5
10. 1- α -Toluidino- $\Delta^1:2,4$ -M.	$C_{17}H_{15}O_2N$ (60%)	Colorless plates from hexane.	121°	C: 74.6 H: 8.5	74.7 8.4
11. 3:9-Dimethyl-T.	$C_{16}H_{17}ON$ "	Microscopic plates from alcohol.	279°	N: 6.0	6.2
12. 3:9-Dimethyl-T.	$C_{15}H_{16}NCl$ (70%)	Yellow plates from hexane.	52°	Cl: 14.6	14.5
13. 1- β -Anisidino- $\Delta^1:2,4$ -M.	$C_{17}H_{17}O_2N$ "	Needles from hexane.	85°	C: 70.3 H: 8.3	70.6 8.0
14. 3-Methyl-7-methoxy-T.	$C_{15}H_{17}O_2N$ (80%)	Microcrystals from alcohol.	288°	C: 73.9 H: 7.1	74.1 7.0
15. 3-Methyl-7-methoxy-T.	$C_{15}H_{16}ONCl$ (50%)	Small needles from alcohol.	113°	Cl: 13.4	13.6
16. 1- α -Anisidino- $\Delta^1:2,4$ -M.	$C_{17}H_{15}O_2N$ (63%)	Thick plates from hexane.	99°	C: 70.2 H: 8.0	70.6 8.0
17. 3-Methyl-9-methoxy-T.	$C_{16}H_{17}O_2N$ (55%)	Small plates from alcohol.	135°	C: 73.9 H: 7.2	74.1 7.0
18. 3-Methyl-9-methoxy-T.	$C_{16}H_{16}ONCl$	Plates from hexane.	86°	Cl: 13.7	13.6
19. 1- β -Phenetidino- $\Delta^1:2,4$ -M.	$C_{18}H_{25}O_2N$ (60%)	Prismatic needles from alcohol.	129°	C: 71.0 H: 8.3	71.3 8.2
20. 3-Methyl-7-ethoxy-T.	$C_{18}H_{19}O_2N$ (65%)	Needles from alcohol.	$> 320^\circ$	C: 74.5 H: 7.5	74.7 7.3
21. 3-Methyl-7-ethoxy-T.	$C_{16}H_{16}ONCl$ (70%)	Needles from hexane.	117°	Cl: 12.7	12.9
22. 1- α -Phenetidino- $\Delta^1:2,4$ -M.	$C_{18}H_{23}O_2N$ (65%)	Lustrous flakes from hexane.	137°	C: 71.1 H: 8.0	71.3 8.2
23. 3-Methyl-9-ethoxy-T.	$C_{16}H_{17}O_2N$ (50%)	Prismatic needles from alcohol.	203°	C: 74.4 H: 7.2	74.7 7.3
24. 3-Methyl-9-ethoxy-T.	$C_{16}H_{15}ONCl$ (70%)	Tiny plates from alcohol.	107°	Cl: 12.8	12.9
25. 1-Anilino- $\Delta^1:2,5$ -M.	$C_{16}H_{14}O_2N$ (70%)		98°	C: 74.7 H: 8.6	74.1 8.1
26. 2-Methyl-T.	$C_{16}H_{15}ON$ (60%)		345°	C: 78.9 H: 6.9	78.8 7.0

1-Methyltetrahydro-5-chloroacridine.—A mixture of 1-methyltetrahydroacridine (2.1 g.), PCl_5 (2.0 g.) and POCl_3 (3.0 c.c.) was heated for 1½ hours at 120°-130°, after the vigorous initial reaction had subsided. After removal of POCl_3 , the contents were decomposed by ice-cold water when an almost clear solution was obtained. The clear filtrate was made alkaline with dilute ammonia when a flocculent yellow precipitate was obtained. It crystallised from petrol (b.p. 50°-60°) in pale yellow thick plates, m.p. 76°, yield 70%. The chloroacridine dissolved in dilute HCl with a faint green fluorescence. (Found: Cl, 15.4. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{NCl}$ requires Cl, 15.3 per cent).

1-Methyltetrahydro-5-anilinoacridine (III: R=Ph).—A mixture of the above 1-methyltetrahydro-5-chloroacridine (1.2 g.), aniline (0.5 g.) and freshly precipitated copper (0.05 g.) was heated in a hard-glass tube at 170°-180° for 10 hours. The resulting solid was washed with ether, and dissolved in water. On the addition of dilute ammonia solution, the base was obtained as a yellow solid which crystallised from benzene in long yellow needles, m.p. 193-94°, yield 65%. It is easily soluble in alcohol as well as in dilute HCl. (Found: N, 9.6. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2$ requires N, 9.7 per cent).

1-Methyltetrahydro-5-toluidinoacridine, similarly prepared from 1-methyltetrahydro-5-chloroacridine (1.2 g.) and *p*-toluidine (0.6 g.), crystallised from benzene in lustrous yellow leaflets, m.p. 157-58°, yield 75%. (Found: N, 9.1. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2$ requires N, 9.2 per cent).

1-Methyltetrahydro-5-piperidinoacridine was similarly obtained from the 1-methyltetrahydro-5-chloroacridine (1.2 g.) and piperidine (1.7 g.) and crystallised from benzene in orange-yellow leaflets, m.p. 137-38°, yield 45%. (Found: N, 9.7. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2$ requires N, 10.0 per cent).

As the experimental details of the condensation of *o*-toluidine, *o*-anisidine, *o*-phenetidine, *p*-toluidine, *p*-anisidine and *p*-phenetidine with ethyl 6-methylcyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylate and the preparation of other derivatives are similar to those described of aniline, their physical and chemical properties are only listed in Table I.

The experimental details of the condensation of ethyl 4-methylcyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylate with various amines, their cyclisation to 3-methyltetrahydro-5-acridones and the conversion of the latter into 3-methyltetrahydro-5-chloroacridines are similar to those of ethyl 6-methylcyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylate. The results are listed in Table II, which also includes the synthesis of 2-methyltetrahydro-5-acridone from ethyl 5-methylcyclohexan-1-one-2-carboxylate and aniline (25 and 26), though it has been prepared by Borsche and Tiedke's method by Perkin and Sedgwick.